

Identifying Cybersecurity Vulnerabilities in Water and Resource Recovery Facilities (WRRFs)

I. Rodríguez-Roda*, D. Palma-Heredia*, L. Arantegui**, S. Bonillo**, S. Kemp***

*LEQUIA, Institute of the Environment, University of Girona, C/ M^a Aurèlia Capmany, 69, 17003 Girona, Spain (E-mail: ignasi.rodriguezroda@udg.edu)

**Càtedra INCIBE, UdG

*** Grup de Recerca en Justícia i Penologia, Departament de Dret Públic, UdG

Abstract

Cybersecurity in Water and Resource Recovery Facilities (WRRFs) has gained importance as recent trends in digitalisation have increased operational efficiency but also exposure and vulnerability to cyber attacks. Through a literature review and interviews with Spanish experts, current top cyber threats to WRRFs and water sector cybersecurity maturity are examined. Results show a lack of available data on cyber threats, as well as a lack of expertise in cybersecurity and that management of the digital infrastructure of WRRFs can be improved. The new legislative framework regarding cyber-incidents underscores that it is necessary to carefully map the digital infrastructure and minimise human error to foster better protection against cyber-threats in WRRFs.

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Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

critical infrastructures; cybersecurity; digitalization; wastewater; WRRF

INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation of water systems allows water infrastructures to operate more efficiently (Torfs, Nicolai, et al., 2022; Malka, Gaska, et al., 2022; de Vitry, Schneider, et al., 2019). In particular, Water and Resource Recovery Facilities (WRRFs) have been greatly enhanced through the implementation of digital technologies in both physical and biological processes. Various examples can be found in the use and optimisation of automated control systems for complex processes such as aeration, or performance prediction from a dynamic influent.

However, from the perspective of cyber-physical-human-systems, concerns have arisen regarding cybersecurity in critical infrastructure like the urban water cycle because of the potential damage attacks can cause to society (Malatji, Marnewick, et al., 2021; You, 2022). Critical infrastructure refers to any asset or system, which is essential for the maintenance of vital societal functions, health, safety, security, economic or the well-being of people, and the disruption or destruction of which would have a significant impact as result of the failure to maintain those functions (EU briefing 2021). It comprises sectors, such as energy or finance, as specified in the legislative framework known as NIS1 (Network and Information Systems), which was recently expanded with the introduction of the NIS2 legal framework through Directive (EU) 2022/2555. This is relevant to WRRFs because, whilst the NIS1 only included the drinking water sector, the NIS2 also includes the wastewater sector (European Commission, n.d.). Thus, WRRFs currently face increasing pressure to adapt to both cybersecurity threats and the corresponding legislative framework.

The objective of this work is to identify the most common types of cyberattacks against WRRFs, as well as the typical vulnerabilities within WRRFs that allow these to occur. Moreover, we will analyse the cybersecurity maturity of the water sector to deal with current threats and what can be done to improve responses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cyber-events databases from different countries, technical reports and scientific publications were

explored to gather evidence data of the frequency and impact of cyber-attacks on WRRFs. Also, interviews with expert practitioners from the water and wastewater sector in Spain were conducted to identify sector-specific concerns and threats from the practitioners' perspective.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Vulnerability of WRRFs against cyber-attacks

Identification of digital assets of WRRFs is a crucial task to understand where and how cyber-attacks might occur.

As water utilities are digitalized, they are also getting involved into the IT-OT-IoT convergence paradigm. The fundamental proposal about this convergence is that all digital devices must be organised and connected as one system (Ebert, 2024). The IoT framework proposes, for example, four main layers of sensing, communication network, data processing and applications (and in some cases a fifth layer regarding business and customer management). This convergence has been given increasing attention because of its potential to enhance supply chains (Rahimi, Maghsoudi, et al., 2024).

As shown in Figure 1, cybersecurity threats such as ransomware and DDoS affect elements from both IT and OT-related layers (mostly they target key elements such as the communication network). However, there is a lack of fundamental knowledge about cybersecurity in the water sector (Thomani, 2021). This situation can be another barrier for the correct implementation of Water and Resource Recovery Facilities (WRRF) technologies.

Figure 1. IT, OT and IoT convergence. IoT layers (Sensors, Communication, Data Processing and Applications) are intertwined between the IT and OT conventional frameworks.

Ransomware is often introduced via social engineering techniques such as phishing. It usually targets servers containing sensitive data and OT-monitoring and control systems such as SCADAs. On the other hand, DDoS mostly aims to disrupt communication network in order to freeze the target's operations. Both DDoS and ransomware can lead to threatening scenarios. For example, through ransomware, cyber-attackers can access control systems and modify operational parameters, whilst DDoS disables the communication network of the victim so it cannot correct the controlling malfunction. This combination of OT-sequestration and manipulation and network

disabling can lead to potential widespread operational damage to the plant and/or to the environment. As the IT environment is steadily increasing protection against vulnerabilities, the professionals interviewed fear that the hackers could turn to OT devices, performing attacks which could have devastating effects not only in economic or reputational terms, but also for public health.

Data availability of cyber-attacks at critical infrastructures

The following databases were accessed: the Cyber Events Database (School of Public Policy - University of Maryland), with a total of 13,471 cases for the period 2018-2023, out of which 3,577 took place in Europe, and from those only 19 were related to the water and wastewater sector; the European Repository of Cyber Incidents (EuRepoC), which contains 2,658 cases for the years 2000-2023, 965 affecting the European region and only 18 related with the water and wastewater sector.

According to the ENISA Threat Landscape 2024 report (European Union Agency for Network and Information Security, 2024), the top three incidents by threat type for last year were DDoS (41%), ransomware (26%) and data-related incidents (19%) against critical infrastructures.

There were reports of several DDoS threat type incidents affecting the OT of multiple water utilities in the US, a wastewater plant in Poland, a hydroelectric dam in France and water pumps in Israel. These are some examples of DDoS-related vulnerabilities in the water sector, which highly depends on the performance of digital technologies.

Interviews

15 interviews with professionals from the Spanish water and wastewater sector. According to results of these interviews, there is a consensus about cyber-attacks becoming increasingly frequent in these critical infrastructures. However, there is a lack of publicly available data. Keeping a high level of awareness about the damaging potential of the attacks is crucial. Furthermore, as with all cyber-attacks against critical infrastructures, they can have a very negative effect on public opinion. This may be why these events have rarely been registered and, thus, there is a lack of historical data regarding cyber-attacks against water infrastructures. Current legislative changes, like the European Directive NIS2, aim to foster transparency and quality data collection about cyber-attacks on critical infrastructures. Nonetheless, there is very little knowledge about the NIS2 requirements among the professionals in the water sector.

Some of the most common consequences of lack of knowledge and awareness about cybersecurity in the WRRF sector are:

1. Digital infrastructures may be outdated and frequently poorly managed (such as fragmentation of digital assets in independent IT and OT departments).
2. Lack of specialized staff with knowledge of cybersecurity or mapping of digital assets.
3. Lack of tools to detect cyber-attacks, so they often go unnoticed.

CONCLUSIONS

WRRF vulnerabilities have been identified across different types of digital assets. Some of these vulnerabilities come from a lack of knowledge and awareness of the cybersecurity threat, but there is already enough evidence to raise the alarm. However, further data regarding WRRFs cyber-attacks and more in-depth analysis of responses from the interviewed practitioners' are required. Still, some preliminary conclusions can be drawn in this regard.

First, it is necessary to know a WRRFs' digital assets in detail: mapping all the elements, connections and data flows is the first step to understanding how a cyber-attack can impact the WRRF. Furthermore, it is recommended to set aside the increasingly obsolete concepts of IT and OT and adopt IoT frameworks to enhance management of the digital system as a whole.

On the other hand, phishing is the most frequent way for ransomware cyber-attacks, and it appeals directly to professionals through social engineering and impersonation. The common proposed solutions against phishing involve user activity registers and careful supervision of human resources. However, protection ultimately relies on the acquisition of minimal cybersecurity awareness and knowledge by all professionals, users and entities interacting with any part of the IoT architecture, as well as internal reaction protocols that limit the potential success of social engineering attacks.

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REFERENCES

- (EuRepoC), E. R. of C. I. European Repository of Cyber Incidents. 2022. [online] <https://eurepoc.eu/database/>.
- Ebert, C. (2024) Convergence of IT, OT, and the IoT. *Computer*, **57**(8), 108–112.
- European Commission The NIS2 Directive Explained. [online] <https://nis2directive.eu/> (Accessed December 27, 2024).
- European Union Agency for Network and Information Security (2024) *ENISA Threat Landscape 2024*,
- Malatji, M., Marnewick, A. L., and von Solms, S. (2021) Cybersecurity Policy and the Legislative Context of the Water and Wastewater Sector in South Africa. *SUSTAINABILITY*, **13**(1).
- Malka, P., Gaska, K., Wysowska, E., Kudlik, K., and Ciula, J. (2022) Intelligent infrastructure (critical) of the water supply network for collective water supply systems - a case study. *DESALINATION AND WATER TREATMENT*, **274**(2nd International Conference on Critical Infrastructure of Cities (CIC) CL-Rytro, POLAND), 1–6.
- Rahimi, M., Maghsoudi, M., and Shokouhyar, S. (2024) The convergence of IoT and sustainability in global supply chains: Patterns, trends, and future directions. *Computers & Industrial Engineering*, **197**, 110631. [online] <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360835224007538>.
- School of Public Policy - University of Maryland Cyber Events Database. [online] <https://cissm.umd.edu/research-impact/publications/cyber-events-database-home> (Accessed December 27, 2024).
- Thomani, R. Z.- (2021) *Cybersecurity Knowledge Requirements for a Water Sector Employee*, Torfs, E., Nicolai, N., Daneshgar, S., Copp, J. B., Haimi, H., Ikumi, D., Johnson, B., Plosz, B. B., Snowling, S., Townley, L. R., Valverde-Perez, B., Vanrolleghem, P. A., Vezzaro, L., and Nopens, I. (2022) The transition of WRRF models to digital twin applications. *WATER SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, **85**(10), 2840–2853.
- de Vitry, M. M., Schneider, M. Y., Wani, O., Manny, L., Leitao, J. P., and Eggimann, S. (2019) Smart urban water systems: what could possibly go wrong? *ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH LETTERS*, **14**(8).
- You, J. (2022) Strengthening Cybersecurity of Water Infrastructure through Legislative Actions. *JOURNAL OF THE AMERICAN WATER RESOURCES ASSOCIATION*, **58**(2), 282–288.

